

Selective Low-Temperature Oxidative Dehydrogenation of Propane over Alumina-Supported Copper Nanoparticles with O₂ and CO₂ as Oxidants

Karolína Simkovičová^{1,2}, Muhammad I. Qadir¹, Naděžda Žilková¹, Joanna E. Olszówka¹, Libor Kvítek², Mariana Klementová³, Esther de Prado³ and Štefan Vajda^{1,*}

¹ Department of Nanocatalysis, J. Heyrovský Institute of Physical Chemistry of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Dolejškova 2155/3, 18200 Prague, Czech Republic; karolina.simkovicova@jh-inst.cas.cz (K.S.); irfan@ufg.br (M.I.Q.); nadezda.zilkova@jh-inst.cas.cz (N.Ž.); joanna.olszowka@jh-inst.cas.cz (J.E.O.)

² Department of Physical Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Palacký University Olomouc, 17. Listopadu 12, 77900 Olomouc, Czech Republic; libor.kvitek@upol.cz

³ Department of Material Analysis, FZU—Institute of Physics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Na Slovance 2, 18200 Prague, Czech Republic; klemari@fzu.cz (M.K.); prado@fzu.cz (E.d.P.)

* Correspondence: stefan.vajda@jh-inst.cas.cz

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Table S1: The comparison of propylene selectivity (%) and propylene rate (molecule \cdot atom $^{-1}\cdot$ s $^{-1}$) of Cu/nanoAl $_2$ O $_3$ and Cu/Al $_2$ O $_3$ with cluster catalysts in propane ODH with oxygen (ratio 1:1).

	Propane conversion (%)	Propylene selectivity (%)	Propylene rate (molecule \cdot atom $^{-1}\cdot$ s $^{-1}$)	Propylene rate (molecule \cdot surface atom $^{-1}\cdot$ s $^{-1}$) approximately	Ref.
Cu/Al $_2$ O $_3$ ^a	24.5	8.9	7.6 \cdot 10 $^{-5}$	3.5 \cdot 10 $^{-4}$	this work
Cu/nanoAl $_2$ O $_3$ ^a	26.2	13.4	1.5 \cdot 10 $^{-4}$	3.1 \cdot 10 $^{-4}$	this work
Cu $_4$ /Al $_2$ O $_3$ ^b	/	79.2	1.5		[1]
Cu $_4$ /UNCD ^b	/	67.8	0.6		[1]
Cu $_{12}$ /Al $_2$ O $_3$ ^b	/	82.9	1.5		[1]
Cu $_{20}$ /Al $_2$ O $_3$ ^b	/	84.0	1.3		[1]
Pt $_{8-10}$ /SnO/Al $_2$ O $_3$ ^c	25.7	68.0	2.9		[2]

^a T = 550 $^{\circ}$ C and propane space velocity 3.9 \cdot 10 $^{-3}$ molecules \cdot atom $^{-1}\cdot$ s $^{-1}$ (WHSV 0.2 h $^{-1}$)

^b T = 550 $^{\circ}$ C and propane space velocity approx. 20.6 molecules \cdot atom $^{-1}\cdot$ s $^{-1}$ (WHSV 7.42 \times 10 4 h $^{-1}$)

^c T = 550 $^{\circ}$ C and propane space velocity 15.1 molecules \cdot atom $^{-1}\cdot$ s $^{-1}$ (WHSV 5.44 \times 10 4 h $^{-1}$)

Cu $_4$ cluster deposited on Al $_2$ O $_3$ layer made by atomic layer deposition (ALD) was measured in a reaction cell of 30 cm 3 volume, the calculated rate of the clusters is around 1.5 molecules \cdot atom $^{-1}\cdot$ s $^{-1}$, which compared to the powder Cu/nanoAl $_2$ O $_3$ (with nanoparticles around 5 nm in size) catalyst would be around twice more active per atom when assuming the same conditions (reactant flow and number of atoms). This difference arises because in nanoparticles most atoms are buried in the bulk and are less accessible for catalysis, whereas clusters have a much higher fraction of surface atoms directly involved in the reaction.

The cluster catalyst, consisting of platinum atoms and two-monolayer-thick SnO deposited on a Al $_2$ O $_3$ ALD layer, demonstrates higher selectivity to propylene (68.0%) compared to the powder catalyst Cu/nanoAl $_2$ O $_3$ (13.4%). If we assume identical conditions, the cluster catalyst would be about 5 times more active in terms of propylene rate.

With an abundance in Earth's crust roughly 12 000 times greater than platinum, copper presents a significant cost advantage, as platinum is currently 3 700 times more expensive per kilogram. Despite the price of platinum being about half that of copper per experiment, the cost-effectiveness of the Cu/(nano)Al $_2$ O $_3$ powder catalysts remains appealing, as the higher cost of platinum can add up in larger-scale applications.

Figure S1: Conversion of propane and product selectivity of a), b) nanoAl₂O₃ and c), d) Al₂O₃. Gas concentration in the reaction mixture: 0.75% propane and 0.75% O₂ in He.

Figure S2: Conversion of propane and product selectivity of a), b) nanoAl₂O₃ and c), d) Al₂O₃. Gas concentration in the reaction mixture: 0.75% propane and 0.25% O₂ in He.

Figure S3: Conversion of propane and product selectivity of a), b) nanoAl₂O₃ and c), d) Al₂O₃. Gas concentration in the reaction mixture: 0.75% propane and 0.75% CO₂ in He.

Table S2: Conversion of propane and product selectivity of Cu/nanoAl₂O₃ at different conditions.

Catalyst	Conditions	T [°C]	X [%]	S _{C₃H₆} [%]	S _{CO₂} [%]	S _{C₂H₄} [%]	S _{CH₃} [%]	r [mol.g ⁻¹ .s ⁻¹]	
Cu/nanoAl ₂ O ₃	1:1 *	250	4.4	48.3	51.7			2.64	
		300	7.8	36.8	63.2			4.68	
		350	8.5	24.8	75.2			4.71	
		400	19.6	11.2	88.1	0.7		11.73	
		450	29.0	5.8	92.0	1.7	0.4	17.34	
		500	29.4	7.0	90.1	2.0	0.9	17.63	
		550	26.2	13.4	80.9	3.4	2.3	15.69	
	3:1 #	250	2.0	48.4	51.6			1.19	
		300	2.4	46.5	53.5			1.24	
		350	6.2	26.4	73.6			3.69	
		400	10.1	13.2	86.8			6.04	
		450	11.2	12.7	81.7	5.5		6.68	
		500	11.9	17.6	76.6	4.3	1.5	7.12	
		550	11.4	36.2	54.0	7.2	2.6	6.81	
	CO ₂ †	250							
		300	0.7	100.0	-				0.42
		350	1.2	100.0	-				0.71
		400	2.0	100.0	-				1.20
		450	2.3	100.0	-				1.40
		500	2.4	100.0	-				1.46
		550	2.4	69.5	-	10.7	19.8		1.42

* The reaction mixture was 0.75% propane and 0.75% O₂ in He

The reaction mixture was 0.75% propane and 0.25% O₂ in He

† The reaction mixture was 0.75% propane and 0.75% CO₂ in He

T = reaction temperature, X = propane conversion at T, S_{product} = product selectivity at T, r = total rate of products of propane ODH per gram of copper at T.

Table S3: Conversion of propane and product selectivity of Cu/Al₂O₃ at different conditions.

Catalyst	Conditions	T [°C]	X [%]	S _{C₃H₆} [%]	S _{CO₂} [%]	S _{C₂H₄} [%]	S _{CH₃} [%]	r [mol.g ⁻¹ .s ⁻¹]	
Cu/Al ₂ O ₃	1:1 *	250	0.5	73.4	26.6			0.35	
		300	0.7	49.8	50.2			0.24	
		350	4.8	41.2	58.8			2.39	
		400	12.6	26.6	73.4			6.31	
		450	21.5	17.2	82.8			10.72	
		500	23.6	10.4	85.2	4.5		11.79	
		550	24.5	8.9	84.4	5.4	1.3	12.20	
	3:1 #	250	1.2	54.8	45.3			0.60	
		300	1.7	66.6	33.4			0.87	
		350	2.4	53.6	46.4			1.22	
		400	6.9	41.7	58.3			3.43	
		450	9.3	25.6	67.8	6.6		4.62	
		500	9.3	32.8	48.4	16.2	2.6	4.66	
		550	9.2	38.1	44.0	15.2	2.8	4.59	
	CO ₂ †	250							
		300	0.3	100.0	-				0.67
		350	1.2	100.0	-				0.68
		400	1.4	83.3	-	16.7			0.69
		450	1.6	66.0	-	34.0			0.80
		500	1.9	60.8	-	39.2			0.93
		550	2.0	68.3	-	29.1	2.5		0.98

* The reaction mixture was 0.75% propane and 0.75% O₂ in He

The reaction mixture was 0.75% propane and 0.25% O₂ in He

† The reaction mixture was 0.75% propane and 0.75% CO₂ in He

T = reaction temperature, X = propane conversion at T, S_{product} = product selectivity at T, r = total rate of products of propane ODH per gram of copper at T.

Figure S4: a,b) SEM images of fresh and spent nanoAl₂O₃; c,e) TEM images of fresh nanoAl₂O₃; d,f) TEM images of spent nanoAl₂O₃.

Figure S5: a,b) SEM images of fresh and spent Al_2O_3 ; c,e) TEM images of fresh Al_2O_3 ; d,f) TEM images of spent Al_2O_3 .

Figure S6: The selected area electron diffraction patterns of a) fresh nanoAl₂O₃, b) spent nanoAl₂O₃, c) fresh Al₂O₃ and d) spent Al₂O₃,

Figure S7: a, b) STEM-HAADF of fresh Cu/nanoAl₂O₃; and c) spent Cu/nanoAl₂O₃. d, e) EDX elemental mapping of fresh and f) spent Cu/nanoAl₂O₃.

Figure S8: XRD patterns of a) fresh and spent nanoAl₂O₃ and b) fresh and spent Al₂O₃.

Table S4: Fractions of various forms of aluminium oxide and hydroxide components in the fresh and spent blanks, obtained from XRD data using Rietveld refinement of the analysis.

Catalyst	Catalyst composition					
	α -Al ₂ O ₃ [%]	θ -Al ₂ O ₃ [%]	κ -Al ₂ O ₃ [%]	α -Al(OH) [%]	β -Al(OH) [%]	Al(OH)-aortic [%]
fresh nanoAl ₂ O ₃	29 ± 2	57 ± 1	-	8 ± 1	4 ± 1	2 ± 1
spent nanoAl ₂ O ₃	34 ± 2	66 ± 2	-	-	-	-
fresh Al ₂ O ₃	45 ± 4	37 ± 5	18 ± 2	-	-	-
spent Al ₂ O ₃	46 ± 4	36 ± 5	18 ± 2	-	-	-

Figure S9: Adsorption isotherms of a) fresh and spent Cu/nanoAl₂O₃, b) fresh and spent nanoAl₂O₃, c) fresh and spent Cu/Al₂O₃ and d) fresh and spent Al₂O₃

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